

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND DIPOLE MOMENT OF DDT

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Commercial DDT was purified by recrystallising from absolute alcohol, the melting point of pure compound being 108.5-109°. The dipole moment of *p*:*p'*-DDT in pure molten state as well as in benzene, carbon tetrachloride and dioxane solutions were determined and explained as due to free rotation of the groups along different bonds. The dehydrochlorinated product, *p*:*p'*-(Cl.C₆H₄)₂C=CCl₂ being a symmetrical compound is shown to be nonpolar. The dipole moments of the compounds related to DDT have also been recalculated by applying the new equation. The toxicity of the *o*:*p'*-, *m*:*p'*- and *p*:*p'*-DDT has been calculated by applying the law of mass action and it has been shown that the log of mortality coefficient (*K*) varies linearly with the dipole moment, *p*:*p'*-DDT with lowest moment (1.1D) being the most toxic compound in this series.

The discovery by Müller (Swiss Patent, 226180, 1940) of the remarkable insecticidal properties of DDT has created great interest. This product is obtained by condensation of chloral (its alcoholate or hydrate) with chlorobenzene, and consists essentially of a mixture of two isomers, 1-trichloro-2:2-bis-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-ethane, called *p*:*p'*-DDT and trichloro-2-*o*-chlorophenyl-2-*p*-chlorophenylethane (called *o*:*p'*-DDT) together with minor constituents of *o*:*o'*-DDT (West and Campbell, *Chem. Ind.*, 1945, 20, 154). Studies leading to the discovery of DDT as an insecticide were first presented by Lauger, Martin and Müller (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 892). The insecticidal properties of DDT and its related compounds have been reviewed in great detail by Haller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1561; *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1945, 39, 467).

Although DDT is chemically unreactive and stable to long boiling with water, it readily loses hydrochloric acid to alcoholic alkali or on mere boiling to form *p*:*p'*-bis-4-chlorophenyl-(1:1)-dichloroethane, *p*:*p'*-(Cl.C₆H₄)₂C=CCl₂. This compound as well as 4:4'-dichlorobenzophenone and bis-(4-chlorophenyl)-acetic acid are almost inactive both as stomach and contact poisons. According to Martin and Wein (*Nature*, 1944, 154, 512) the toxicity of *p*:*p'*-DDT is due to its chemisorption at vital centres by interferences with essential enzyme system after intercellular decomposition to form hydrochloric acid and the ethylene derivative. As the ethylene derivative is nontoxic, the toxicity is ascribed to the hydrogen chloride. Diphenyltrichloroethane also readily loses hydrochloric acid in presence of alkali, yet it is relatively nontoxic. An additional factor, *lipoid solubility* of the molecule, as a whole, is therefore operative. The chlorophenyl group of the DDT is highly *lipoid soluble*.

We have studied the dielectric properties of DDT and related compounds with a view to correlating their insecticidal properties with the electric moments.

EXPERIMENTAL

The commercial DDT melts over a wide range of temperature as it contains different isomers and related compounds. The commercial DDT was recrystallised twice from absolute alcohol, melting point of the product obtained was 108.5°-109°, in agreement with the value reported by Haller *et al* (*loc. cit.*). The mother-liquor contained *o*:*p'*-DDT. *p*:*p'*-DDT on boiling with ethanolic potassium hydroxide gave dehydrochlorinated product, 1:1-dichloro-2:2-bis-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-ethylene, m.p. at 88-89°.

DDT is relatively unstable at temperatures above 120° and in presence of metallic

salts (Martin *et. al.*, *loc. cit.*). Molten DDT was found to decompose in presence of finely divided carbon.

The dipole moments of DDT in pure molten form, as well as in benzene and carbon tetrachloride solution, and also of dehydrochlorinated DDT were determined by the present author (*Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1945, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, Abst. No. 33). The dipole moments of 12 derivatives of diphenyltrichloroethane were determined by Wild (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 892). These results have been recalculated by employing the new equation (Jatkar *et al.*, *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1946, 28A, Part II).

$$P = \frac{(\epsilon - 1)M}{d}; P_2 = \frac{(n^2 - 1)M}{d} \text{ and}$$

$$P - P_2 = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{kT} \text{ for pure liquid and}$$

$$P_{12} = \frac{(\epsilon - 1)(M_1 f_1 + M_2 f_2)}{d_{12}} = P_1 f_1 + P_2 f_2 \text{ and } P_2 - P_2 = \frac{4\pi N \mu^2}{kT}$$

for solutions.

The corresponding electronic polarisation was calculated from the atomic refraction [cf. Kucken and Wolf, "Hand und Jahrbuch der chemisch physik", 1935, (6), A-B] The results are shown in the following table.

TABLE I

1. p : p' -DDT (a) : Pure liquid. $P_2 = 335.9$				
Temp.	d .	ϵ .	P .	$\mu \times 10^{18}$.
145°	1.348	2.381	481.2	1.05
130°	1.361	2.852	481.6	1.03
110°	1.380	2.884	490.3	1.03
104°	1.388	2.900	485.9	1.00
Solvent = CCl ₄ . Temp. = 25° (a).				
f_2 .	d .	ϵ .	P_2 .	$\mu \times 10^{18}$.
0.05888	1.545	2.393	631.7	1.12
Solvent = dioxane. Temp. = 25° (a).				
w_2 .	d .	ϵ .	P_2 .	$\mu \times 10^{18}$.
0.1115	1.0633	2.2614	644	1.19
Solvent = benzene. Temp. = 20° (b)				
f_2 .	d .	ϵ .	P_2 .	$\mu \times 10^{18}$.
0.00201	0.8778	2.2875	566.119	1.12
0.00506	0.8825	2.2963	571.877	1.12
0.01023	0.8910	2.3080	538.798	1.03
0.01551	0.8990	2.3205	536.828	1.03
2. Dehydrochlorinated DDT : Solvent = benzene. Temp. = 27° (a) $P_2 = 287$.				
f_2 .	d .	ϵ .	P_2 .	$\mu \times 10^{18}$.
0.01124	0.8868	2.2387	54.26	0

(a) Present author.

(b) Recalculated from the data by H. Wild (1944).

TABLE II
Table of moments

Substance.	$\mu \times 10^{-18}$.	Substance.	$\mu \times 10^{-18}$.
(1)	2.14		
(2)	1.91		
(3)	2.12		
(4)	1.68		
(5)	2.11		
(6)	2.4		
(13)			2.5

No. 1, 2—Present author.

No. 3—13—Recalculated from the data by H. Wild (1944).

DISCUSSION

The results are summarised in Table II. The applicability of the new equation to the various solutions is fully borne out by the constancy of the results. The small variations of the moment e.g., from 1.00 to 1.05 in the case of pure molten liquid and also 1.03 to 1.11 in the case of benzene solution are within the limits of experimental errors, as also the moments obtained from dioxane and carbon tetrachloride viz., 1.12 and 1.19D. Taking the new values of bond moments, C—H 0.4, C—Cl (aliph.) 1.69, C—Cl (arom.) 1.5, the average free rotation value along the various bonds comes to be the same as the observed moment for *p:p'*-DDT.

The dehydrochlorinated compound $(C_6H_4Cl)_2C=CCl_2$ is a symmetrical molecule and should not possess any moment, which is confirmed by the present experimental work.

In the case of dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane, the moment of *p:p'* compound is the least (1.1D) and that of the *o:p'* is the greatest (1.9D), *m:p'* being intermediate (1.55).

The moments of (Table of moments, Table II) *p:p'*-ditolyl-(Müller, *loc. cit.*), 3:3':4:4'-tetramethyl and 2:2':4:4'-tetramethyl-diphenyltrichloroethane are the same (viz., 2.1D) and which correspond to the free rotation along the HC—CCl₃. In the case of 2:2':5:5'-tetramethyldiphenyltrichloroethane (West and Campbell, *loc. cit.*) the methyl groups being at *p:p'* position, the small moment due to CH₃ groups is cancelled and the resultant moment (1.66 D) is the same as that of diphenyltrichloroethane (Müller, *loc. cit.*).

Toxicity and the Dipole Moment of DDT and related Compounds

It has been observed that in this series of compounds only DDT has highest insecticidal property. The mortality coefficients of these compounds have been calculated by applying the law of unimolecular reaction,

$$Kc = \frac{2.3}{t} \log \frac{100}{100-x}$$

where x is the % of insects killed in time t . (The full paper will be published elsewhere). The values are given in the following table.

TABLE III

Compound.	Mortality coefficient K .	$x \times 10^3$	Log K .
<i>p:p'</i> - DDT	14.6	1.10	1.16
<i>m:p'</i> -DDT	2.6	1.55	0.42
<i>o:p'</i> - DDT	1.3	1.90	0.21

It is interesting to point out the linear relationship between the logarithm of mortality coefficient and the dipole moment, as the moment increases, the mortality coefficient decreases, the compound DDT with lowest dipole moment (1.1D) being the most toxic insecticide ($K=14.6$).

Thanks of the author are due to Dr. S. K. K. Jatkar for guidance and to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for the financial help during this investigation.